

Women's success in academic leadership should be more robust

Women's success in academic leadership challenges stereotypes and is subject to backlash and resistance. Success rests on individual effort and accomplishment but also reflects alignment with the academic power system and support from others. Appreciation of the systemic and collective aspects of success is essential for women's success to be robust.

The article reflects the personal opinion of the author and does not necessarily reflect the position of SCNAT.

Is a woman successful when she has achieved a position of academic leadership? Although this is often assumed, it is not always true. Success can be compromised if a leader leaves her position prematurely or involuntarily or fails to accomplish her most important goals. The term 'glass cliff' describes the observation that women (or minorities) are offered leadership opportunities in situations where success is very likely to be fragile.¹ Historical cases, such as the short tenure of Prof. Denise Denton as Chancellor of the University of California, Santa Cruz and its tragic conclusion,² illustrate the intense hostility that can be directed toward women in positions of academic leadership. Recent and highly-publicized reports of women's deficits in academic leadership have raised questions of gender bias and discrimination in the reporting on such cases and in the institutional, systemic support that is essential for individual success in leadership.³ Women in positions of academic leadership should be aware that success can be fleeting and solutions can be fragile.

Success in context

Success is never the result just of individual effort and accomplishment since it occurs within a specific context and system. Systemic factors influence success for both men and women. Women, however, must achieve success within academic systems that have been shaped by stereotypical and gender-biased expectations. Examples include the exclusivity of academic success and the strong focus on a single individual as the leader of a research group. This is not well aligned with the community-oriented character traits attributed to women. Since these norms favor the advancement of men, women (and minorities) must pay more attention to systemic and institutional factors that can impede or compromise success.

Diversity brings success

To achieve robust success in academic leadership, women need to formulate our own leadership goals clearly and understand their potential for implementation within the academic system. In a recent post on the 500 Women Scientists Fribourg-Bern blog,⁴ I posed eight questions to women embarking on academic leadership: (1) what do you want to accomplish in your leadership position? (2) what constraints will you have to deal with? (3) what resources will you have at your disposal? (4) what trade-offs will you make to accommodate your new responsibilities? (5) who will you be able to depend on for advice and support? (6) what are the leverage points for change in your organization? (7) how is information shared in your organization? and (8) what are the formal and informal power structures in your organization?

I am convinced that robust success for women in academic leadership will require that we go beyond individual solutions. As the feminist Carol Hanisch wrote, "There are no personal solutions... There is only collective action for a collective solution."⁵ Women in academics share many of the concerns that have been expressed by early career researchers and have also been actively engaged in various initiatives to make the academic system more inclusive, supportive, and sustainable.⁶ Increasing gender diversity has been shown to produce more novel and higher-impact scientific ideas.⁷ I believe that diversifying academic leadership will be critical to ensuring the future success of the academic enterprise.

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[https://scnat.ch/en/uuid/i/7b278582-6de7-5ccc-8c7a-121644b92068-I did it Experiences from leading scientists](https://scnat.ch/en/uuid/i/7b278582-6de7-5ccc-8c7a-121644b92068-I%20did%20it%20Experiences%20from%20leading%20scientists)

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¹ Whawell, S. (2018) “Women are shattering the glass ceiling only to fall off the glass cliff”, *The Conversation*. <https://theconversation.com/women-are-shattering-the-glass-ceiling-only-to-fall-off-the-glass-cliff-94071>

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Denice_Denton

³ <https://www.500womenscientistsfribourgbern.ch/lettertotheleadershipofmpg>; Hering, J.G., Croce, R., Escher, B.I., Magurran, A.E., and Noheda, B. (2022) “News stories must account for gender bias”, *Science* (letter to the Editor), 374: 1455-6, <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.abn2559>.

⁴ <https://www.500womenscientistsfribourgbern.ch/post/eight-questions-for-women-embarking-on-academic-leadership>

⁵ Hanisch, C. (2006) The personal is political: The women’s liberation movement classic with a new explanatory introduction. <http://www.carolhanisch.org/CHwritings/PIP.html>

⁶ Hering, J. G., Green, S. A., Heckmann, L., Katehi, L. P. B., Maurice, P. A. & Young, S. (2022). A call for an alliance between female academic leaders and early career researchers to improve the academic STEM system. *Elephant in the Lab*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6514731>

⁷ Yang, Y., T. Y. Tian, T. K. Woodruff, B. F. Jones and B. Uzzi (2022). "Gender-diverse teams produce more novel and higher-impact scientific ideas." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **119**(36): e2200841119.